

Unveiling the Firm-Level Drivers of Information and Communication Innovation: Evidence from Spanish Innovators Using Machine Learning

Angel Peiro-Signes¹[0000-0002-1549-6972] and Marival Segarra-Oña²[0000-0001-9674-9056]

¹ Universitat Politècnica de València, 46022 Valencia, Spain

² Universitat Politècnica de València, 46022 Valencia, Spain
anpeisig@upv.edu.es

Abstract. The growing digitalization of business processes has given rise to a distinct class of innovations focused on communication and information (CI). These innovations, encompassing new algorithms, data architectures, and digital coordination methods, require both technological and organizational integration. Despite their increasing strategic relevance, empirical evidence on the determinants of CI innovation remains limited. This study investigates which firm-level characteristics differentiate CI innovators from other innovative firms, combining insights from the resource-based view and open innovation theory. Using data from the 2018 Spanish Community Innovation Survey (CIS), we apply an interpretable machine learning framework that integrates XGBoost classification, Boruta feature selection, and SHAP-based interpretation to identify the most influential predictors of CI innovation. The model highlights that investment in digital capital, measured as the share of turnover devoted to software development, database work, and data analysis, is the strongest driver of CI innovation. Complementary enablers include technological upgrading through new machinery acquisition and external collaboration in innovation activities, emphasizing the importance of both tangible and relational assets. Conversely, traditional in-house R&D intensity exhibits a limited or even negative influence, suggesting structural inertia in adapting to digital innovation. Financial constraints emerge as a modest but significant barrier, reinforcing the enabling role of access to capital for digital experimentation. These findings contribute to the literature by clarifying the mechanisms through which internal capabilities, external linkages, and financial conditions jointly shape firms' engagement in CI innovation.

Keywords: Information and communication innovation, Digital transformation, Machine learning, Innovation drivers.

1 Introduction

Innovation research has long emphasized that not all innovations are alike. Beyond the distinction between product and process innovations, a growing body of work focuses on a new category: digital or communication and information (CI) innovations [1;2].

These innovations include those related to creating new methods for processing, storing, or communicating information, such as algorithms, data architectures, or internal communication systems. They differ from traditional innovations because they combine technological, organizational, and knowledge-based elements. In today's digital economy, where data and connectivity are embedded in business processes, CI innovations transform how companies coordinate and learn, thereby driving organizational transformation [3].

These CI innovations have received little attention in empirical innovation studies. Analyses have typically focused on R&D or the number of new products without delving deeper into the interaction between digital infrastructure, software, and organizational practices [4; 5]. Developing a new algorithm or an integrated communication platform requires technical expertise as well as the capabilities to integrate these tools into existing workflows and routines [6, 2]. Therefore, as with other innovations, CI innovation requires a multidimensional perspective that connects internal resources, external cooperation, and firm-specific characteristics.

From a resource-based and absorptive capacity perspective [7], firms that invest in digital capabilities, particularly software, databases, and IT systems, build a technological foundation that enables them to identify, absorb, and apply new digital knowledge. In this regard, investment in ICT and software has been shown to positively influence a firm's overall innovation performance [8,9]. However, investment in ICT alone is not enough. CI innovations frequently require the adaptation of existing systems and internal coordination, and success depends on the ability to adapt and integrate these new technologies into daily practices [2,10].

External collaboration is also important for CI innovations. Many data tools, standards, and infrastructures are developed in collaboration with other market actors [11]. This cooperation with universities, research centers, suppliers, or clients provides firms with access to complementary capabilities, helping to overcome internal gaps and reduce uncertainty [12]. Other external stimuli, such as public subsidies or competitive pressure, can also push firms to explore this type of innovation [13,1].

A firm's ability to translate these internal and external efforts into CI innovation may also vary according to its characteristics. Larger firms usually have greater financial and human resources for development, but they face higher organizational rigidity that can slow down adoption. Smaller and younger firms, while typically more flexible, have fewer financial resources, which can limit investment in digital infrastructure [14]. On the other hand, international exposure generally enhances a firm's collaboration network and its innovative capabilities, enabling it to compete in global environments [15]. Conversely, perceived barriers—such as a shortage of qualified personnel, regulatory complexity, or privacy concerns—can restrict CI innovation [16].

The lack of studies that simultaneously incorporate all this complexity and numerous factors suggests a need for data-driven research to indicate what influences firms to innovate in CI and how internal and external factors interact in this process. This study addresses this gap by applying machine learning techniques to a large, nationally representative dataset from the 2018 Spanish Community Innovation Survey (CIS) [17]. By analyzing a major sample of innovative firms across all sectors, this study charac-

terizes the companies that engage in CI innovations. The study provides relevant insights for managers to develop the organizational and technological capabilities that facilitate digital transformation, and for policymakers to design support mechanisms that effectively promote digital innovation across all sectors and firm sizes.

2 Background and Hypotheses

In the taxonomy of innovation, digital (information and communication) innovations are distinct from product or process innovations, although they are related to them. CI innovations, such as new algorithms, data architectures, internal communication protocols, or integrated information systems, require a combination of technical, organizational, and knowledge-based attributes. That is, they go beyond technical novelty because they require integration into existing organizational routines [2]. In this sense, a firm's decision to introduce CI innovations requires a prior evaluation of internal resources, external linkages, and specific constraints.

From a resource-based perspective, firms that already possess or invest in digital and R&D capabilities are in a more favorable position to carry out CI innovations. Previous studies on digital transformation indicate that internal digital investment correlates with greater organizational efficiency, better process integration, and higher overall innovation performance [5]. In fact, when a firm has already invested in IT assets and information systems, it incurs lower fixed costs when launching new CI initiatives. The acquisition or development of software, databases, and IT infrastructure signals the firm's commitment to digitalization, but it also enhances its absorptive capacity for new CI methods. Internal R&D also helps firms identify, assimilate, and apply new external knowledge [7].

However, digital methods typically require a higher degree of organizational flexibility than classic product or process innovation [6], given that CI innovations sometimes require upgrading existing systems and resolving compatibility issues and dependencies, among others. More flexible firms with a culture of experimentation are better positioned to adopt or generate new CI methods [2,3]. Therefore, internal digital investment capabilities, R&D capacity, and structural flexibility constitute fundamental enablers without which CI innovation is less likely.

H1: Among innovators, firms with higher levels of internal digital investment, internal R&D, and organizational flexibility have a higher probability of participating in CI innovation (compared to non-CI-related innovation).

Even the most capable firms rarely innovate alone [11, 18]. For CI innovation, external knowledge usually plays a very important role since many tools, standards, algorithms, or software modules are developed outside the firm. In these cases, collaboration and cooperation with different actors (universities, research institutes, clients, suppliers, or the industry) complement the firm's internal knowledge gaps [11]. In the context of information and communication technologies, cooperation can provide access to new protocols, analytical methods, or shared platforms, thereby reducing the marginal cost of CI innovation. Similarly, firms that leverage patents, trade fairs, or tech-

nology networks are more likely to detect emerging digital trends or techniques. Innovation studies suggest that firms drawing upon diverse sources of external information experience higher innovation performance [12].

Furthermore, external funding, grants, or subsidies can reduce the upfront risk and cost burden of CI innovation. Firms that apply for or receive innovation subsidies typically show a greater willingness to engage in more speculative digital projects [13]. Likewise, market demand for digital functionalities (e.g., IoT, data analytics) exerts competitive pressure that drives firms to adopt or develop CI innovations [1]. All these external factors constitute a second important pillar in explaining a firm's orientation toward CI innovation.

H2: Among innovators, firms that collaborate and utilize external information sources, receive or apply for innovation funding, or face greater demand for digitalization are more likely to adopt CI innovation.

The effectiveness of internal and external drivers in promoting CI innovation might not be uniform across all firms. Firm-specific characteristics, such as size or the perception of barriers, could condition how capabilities and linkages with external actors translate into actual CI outcomes.

Larger firms generally have more resources to absorb the risks and costs of CI innovation. However, their bureaucratization and routines can also limit the agile implementation of new information systems. Innovation studies indicate that size correlates positively with innovation propensity [19]. On the other hand, younger and more agile firms are usually less constrained by legacy systems and can adopt digital innovations more easily than traditional companies [10].

The industrial context is also important. Digital-resource-intensive service firms face lower entry barriers to CI innovation, whereas more traditional sectors like manufacturing require higher implementation and maintenance costs [20]. Moreover, the financial health of these firms allows them to experiment with higher-risk innovations, such as digital and ICT innovation [22].

Export orientation and internationalization can drive CI innovation [21]. Firms operating in external markets often must adopt platform-based systems to compete globally, as well as digital standards from other markets that require the introduction of CI innovations [21].

Finally, CI innovation could be negatively affected if the firm perceives obstacles to its implementation, such as high costs, a lack of internal talent, regulatory or privacy restrictions, or technological uncertainty [16].

H3a: The positive effect of internal capabilities on CI innovation is stronger for firms that are larger, more international, younger, or financially healthier, and weaker under conditions of high perceived barriers.

H3b: The positive effect of external engagement on CI innovation is moderated by firms' perceptions of high barriers to innovation or risk aversion.

3 Methodology

The objective of this study is to uncover which characteristics influence an innovative firm to develop new communication or information (CI) processing methods. Machine learning techniques are utilized to reveal hidden patterns within complex datasets. The model design focused on striking a balance between predictive accuracy and explanatory clarity, prioritizing models capable of capturing complex dependencies among firm-level variables.

The analysis used data from the 2018 Spanish Community Innovation Survey (CIS), which is harmonized at the European level to monitor the innovative behavior of firms. From the complete sample (31,105 firms), a subset of innovative firms (11,216) was selected, of which 4,256 (37.95%) reported CI-related innovations. In some cases, variables were aggregated into higher-order composites to improve their theoretical fit and explanatory capacity. For example, the types of cooperation with public or private actors were grouped together.

Due to class imbalance (CI innovators vs. non-CI innovators), the F1-score metric was selected to evaluate model performance. The F1-score integrates precision and recall to assess the model's ability to correctly classify CI innovators.

Among the various machine learning approaches tested, Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) was selected for its excellent predictive performance, robustness to multicollinearity, and capacity to handle large, heterogeneous datasets. XGBoost builds a sequence of decision trees that iteratively correct the residuals of previous iterations. Its regularized objective function balances fit and complexity, while its internal hyperparameters allow for fine-tuning the model's behavior without excessive preprocessing. To address the class imbalance, the `scale_pos_weight` parameter was used, which boosts the contribution of the minority class without resorting to oversampling or undersampling, thereby preserving both data integrity and computational efficiency.

Table 1. Boruta selected attributes

Selected features	Description
EXP_TOT_SOFT_DBA_rat	Share of turnover spent on software development, database work, and data analysis. It captures firm investment in digital capital for information processing.
PUR_MES_NEW	Indicates whether the firm acquired machinery, equipment, or software based on previously unused technology. It reflects technological upgrading.
COOP_INN_XRND	Indicates collaboration with other enterprises on innovation activities excluding R&D. It captures external sourcing of know-how for integration and implementation.
EXP_INNO_RND_IH_rat_dummy	Dummy variable indicating whether the firm had any internal R&D expenditure relative to turnover. It indicates the presence of in-house exploratory capacity.

COOP_OTH	Captures cooperation on non-innovation-related business activities. It represents broader inter-firm linkages that may support knowledge diffusion.
FUND_DEBT_NSUCC	Indicates whether the firm experienced unsuccessful attempts to obtain debt financing. It indicates the presence of financial constraints potentially inhibiting innovation.

Minimal data preparation was required, as most variables were already in dummy or ordinal categorical formats. Unordered categorical variables, such as industry codes, were converted into dummies using one-hot encoding. After processing, the dataset included over 260 variables.

An initial baseline model was trained using all features and default settings, achieving 68.23% accuracy, an F1-score of 53.61%, and a ROC AUC of 64.37%. While informative, not all variables meaningfully contributed to the predictions, and high dimensionality risked reducing performance. To address this, the Boruta algorithm was employed for feature selection. Unlike model-dependent importance scores, Boruta identifies all relevant variables by comparing each feature to randomized “shadow” features, retaining only those that consistently outperform noise.

The algorithm identified six confirmed features as essential, forming the foundation for subsequent model refinement. This strategic combination of robust machine learning techniques and thoughtful feature selection enabled the reliable classification of firms likely to engage in CI-related innovation.

Using the six features identified by the Boruta algorithm, a new XGBoost model was developed and tuned to optimize performance. Hyperparameter tuning aimed to balance learning efficiency with overfitting control. This process followed a stepwise grid search where the parameters yielding the best F1-scores were kept for subsequent steps.

The final model’s predictive reliability was evaluated based on accuracy and the F1-score. Further interpretability was achieved through Shapley values, which quantified the individual contribution of each feature to the prediction outcomes. This allowed for both the ranking of variable importance and the identification of their directional influence, clarifying how specific firm characteristics increase or decrease the likelihood of CI innovation. This final model, refined through careful tuning and interpretability tools, offers both robust classification and meaningful insights into innovation behavior.

4 Results

After completing the tuning process, the final XGBoost model ($\gamma = 0.1$, $\text{learning_rate} = 0.01$, $\text{max_depth} = 5$, $\text{min_child_weight} = 3$, $n_estimators = 100$, $\text{reg_alpha} = 0.03$, and $\text{scale_pos_weight} = 1.64$) achieved an F1-score of 0.5893, with an accuracy of 67.20%, a recall of 61.97%, and a ROC AUC of 71.63%. These results indicate reasonable performance that surpasses the 25% proportional chance criterion suggested by Hair et al. [23], demonstrating that the model effectively distinguishes between firms

that innovate in information processing or communication (CI) and those that innovate in other areas.

Table 2. Confusion matrix and precision metrics

True\Predicted	Non IC-innovator	IC Innovator	precision	recall	f1-score	support
Non IC-innovator	980	412	0.75	0.70	0.73	1392
IC Innovator	324	528	0.56	0.62	0.59	852
		accuracy			0.67	2244
		macro avg	0.66	0.66	0.66	2244
		weighted avg	0.68	0.67	0.67	2244

The confusion matrix (see Table 2) compares the predicted and actual classes in the test dataset. For non-CI innovators, the model achieved a precision of 0.75 and a recall of 0.70, resulting in an F1-score of 0.73. For CI innovators, precision reached 0.56 and recall was 0.62, yielding an F1-score of 0.59. These outcomes suggest that while the model maintains stronger performance when identifying non-CI innovators, it also captures a substantial proportion of true CI innovators.

Fig. 1 presents the features included in the final XGBoost model, ranked according to their mean absolute SHAP values. The SHAP value measures the average contribution of each variable to the prediction outcome, reflecting its global importance in classifying firms as innovators in information processing or communication (CI). Figure 2 illustrates the distribution of the SHAP values for both classes, showing not only the relevance of each feature but also the direction of its influence on the model’s output.

Fig. 1. Model feature importance and Shap values distribution.

The most relevant variable was EXP_TOT_SOFT_DBA_rat, which represents the share of turnover spent on software development, database work, and data analysis. This indicator captures a firm’s investment in digital capital specifically aimed at enhancing information processing capabilities. Its prominence in the model suggests that dedicating a greater portion of revenue to digital development and data-related activities is a critical driver of CI innovation. The second most important feature, PUR_MES_NEW, reflects the purchase of new machinery or equipment, emphasizing

the role of technological upgrading in enabling firms to implement new methods for processing and communication.

Other important variables include COOP_INN_XRND and COOP_OTH, which capture cooperation in innovation with external partners and other organizations. These results suggest that firms engaging in collaborative innovation networks are more likely to develop CI-related methods. Conversely, EXP_INNO_RND_IH_rat_dummy, which indicates whether a company invested in internal R&D, contributed negatively, showing that investment in in-house R&D activities does not support CI-oriented innovation. Similarly, FUND_DEBT_NSUCC, which denotes unsuccessful attempts to obtain debt financing, exhibited a marginal, negative, and asymmetrical impact. In other words, unsuccessful attempts to obtain debt financing increase the likelihood of a company being classified as a non-CI innovator, but the absence of such unsuccessful attempts does not decrease its likelihood of being classified as a CI innovator.

5 Discussion and Conclusions

This study utilizes advanced machine learning techniques to identify the factors that distinguish innovative firms developing new information processing or communication (CI) methods from those pursuing other forms of innovation. Using data from the 2018 Spanish Community Innovation Survey (CIS), this research provides novel empirical evidence on the interaction among internal capabilities, external linkages, and firm-specific characteristics in shaping digital innovation behavior. Utilizing a large, nationally representative dataset alongside interpretable machine learning models allows for a better understanding of how different attributes collectively determine the adoption of CI innovation, a form of innovation that combines technological, organizational, and informational dimensions.

The results from the XGBoost model demonstrate that investment in digital infrastructure constitutes the strongest predictor of CI innovation. Since investment in ICT/software is positively related to firms' innovation activities (product, process, organizational, etc.) and its effects are stronger when combined with other organizational measures, it is reasonable to assume that investment in software/databases serves as the technological foundation for incorporating CI-type innovation [8,9]. Such investment demonstrates a commitment to digital transformation, but it also enhances absorptive capacity, enabling firms to recognize and integrate external technological knowledge. In this sense, the internal accumulation of technological assets and technical expertise strengthens a firm's innovative potential in digital spheres. This finding aligns with previous research indicating that greater digital transformation is positively associated with firm performance and productivity [2,23].

The second most influential factor is the acquisition of new machinery or equipment. This highlights the complementary relationship between tangible and intangible technological investment. Although CI innovation is primarily carried out in non-physical technologies, such as data analytics or communication protocols, its effective implementation often depends on compatible hardware and infrastructure capable of supporting digital processes. The simultaneous presence of software and hardware investment

indicates that CI innovation thrives in firms that modernize their entire technological foundation [3].

Innovation cooperation emerges as another influential factor. Firms that collaborate with external partners show a higher propensity to innovate in CI. This result aligns with the open innovation perspective [11,18], which indicates that external collaboration provides access to complementary knowledge, technologies, and learning opportunities that internal efforts alone cannot provide. In digital contexts, where standards, algorithms, and tools are often developed collaboratively through networks, these alliances play a decisive role in the diffusion of innovation. Therefore, cooperation acts not only as an enabler of innovation but also as a structural mechanism through which firms integrate themselves into broader technological ecosystems [12,1].

Surprisingly, internal R&D expenditure showed a weak or even negative relationship with CI innovation. While R&D is typically considered a fundamental driver of innovation, this result suggests that conventional R&D—often oriented toward improving physical products or processes—does not automatically translate into digital innovation capability. Firms focused on traditional R&D may struggle with rigid routines that hinder experimentation with new information architectures or communication systems. This observation complements the arguments of Barthel et al. [2] and Bäcklund et al. [6], who noted that the success of digital transformation depends more on organizational adaptability and the ability to integrate digital methods into daily practices than on formal R&D intensity alone.

Financial constraints also played a modest but significant role. Firms that reported unsuccessful attempts to obtain debt financing are less likely to innovate in CI. Developing information-based innovations entails high upfront uncertainty, intangible outcomes, and often long-term returns, which increases perceived risk among financially constrained firms. This finding highlights the asymmetrical nature of financial effects. While a lack of funding can hinder innovation, the availability of resources does not guarantee success unless they are strategically directed toward digital capabilities and collaboration. Therefore, access to capital remains an enabler of digital experimentation [16,9].

These results confirm the three formulated theoretical propositions. First, internal digital capabilities and flexible structures (H1) form the foundation for CI innovation. Second, external engagement through cooperation and information sharing (H2) constitutes a complementary mechanism that provides the necessary knowledge flows for digital experimentation. Third, firm-specific conditions—particularly financial health and perceived barriers (H3a, H3b)—moderate the transition of these capabilities into actual CI outcomes. Although variables such as firm size or age do not appear as direct predictors, they might exert an effect through resource endowment or collaboration capacity.

Methodologically, the combination of XGBoost, Boruta feature selection, and SHAP interpretability offers a robust framework for examining large-scale survey data in the social sciences, contributing to showing how machine learning can identify relevant characteristics to capture the multidimensional nature of innovation systems.

From a managerial perspective, the results highlight that digital investment should not be conceived as an isolated IT expense, but rather as a strategic foundation for innovation. Managers must ensure that digital tools, data systems, and IT infrastructure are integrated across all departments, facilitating seamless information flow and experimentation. Furthermore, cooperation enhances innovation strategy by establishing alliances with research institutions, technology providers, and industry peers, which help firms access cutting-edge knowledge and reduce the uncertainty associated with complex digital projects. Managers should also foster agile project management skills and a culture of continuous learning to improve the integration of CI innovations within firms.

For policymakers, the implications are twofold. First, the results suggest that conventional R&D subsidies might not effectively stimulate CI innovation, as these programs typically focus on tangible or product-based outcomes. Second, measures that alleviate financial barriers, particularly for small and medium-sized enterprises, could broaden participation in digital transformation. Policy instruments should prioritize digital capacity building, supporting investments in data systems, software, and digital collaboration platforms that connect firms with research institutions and technology providers to accelerate the diffusion of innovations.

Several limitations must be acknowledged. The cross-sectional nature of the data restricts causal inference, and the findings reflect the Spanish innovation landscape at a specific point in time. Future research could explore longitudinal data to evaluate how the determinants of CI innovation evolve over time or across economic cycles. Furthermore, while the machine learning model has high predictive accuracy, it cannot capture unmeasured qualitative aspects, such as organizational culture or leaders' attitudes toward digitalization. Combining quantitative models with qualitative case studies would provide more comprehensive explanations of the mechanisms underlying CI innovation.

Acknowledgments. This research received a grant from the Valencian regional government CIAICO/2023/228.

References

1. Yoo, Y. et al.: Organizing for innovation in the digitized world. *Organization Science* **23**(5), 1398–1408 (2012)
2. Barthel, P., Fuchs, C., Birner, B., Hess, T.: *Embedding digital innovations in organizations: A typology for digital innovation units*, pp. 780–795. GITO Verlag (2020)
3. Li, K. et al.: Embedding data science innovations in organizations. *Data-Centric Engineering* **4**, e26 (2023)
4. OECD/Eurostat: *Oslo Manual 2018: Guidelines for Collecting, Reporting and Using Data on Innovation*, 4th edn. OECD Publishing (2018)
5. Jung, J., Gómez-Bengoechea, G.: A literature review on firm digitalization: Drivers and impacts. *Estudios sobre la Economía Española* (20) (2022)
6. Bäcklund, K., Vigren, O., Carlsson, J.: Implementing digital innovations: Overcoming organizational challenges. *Developments in the Built Environment* **18**, 100436 (2024)

Unveiling the Firm-Level Drivers of Information and Communication Innovation

7. Cohen, W. M., Levinthal, D. A.: Absorptive capacity: A new perspective on learning and innovation. *Administrative Science Quarterly* 35(1), 128–152 (1990)
8. Hall, B. H., Lotti, F., Mairesse, J.: Impact of R&D and ICT investments on innovation and productivity in Italian firms. *Economics of Innovation and New Technology* 22(3), 300–328 (2012)
9. Mohnen, P., Polder, M., Van Leeuwen, G.: ICT, R&D, and organizational innovation. In: *Measuring and Accounting for Innovation in the 21st Century*. Univ. of Chicago Press (2019)
10. Tushman, M. L., O'Reilly III, C. A.: Ambidextrous organizations. *California Management Review* 38(4), 8–29 (1996)
11. Chesbrough, H. W. *Open innovation: The new imperative for creating and profiting from technology*. Harvard Business Press, 2003.
12. Peiró-Signes, Á., Díez-Martínez, I., Segarra-Oña, M.: Drivers of cooperation for innovation. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management* 31(4), 2929–2952 (2024)
13. Zuo, Z., Lin, Z.: Government R&D subsidies and firm innovation performance. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge* 7(2), 100176 (2022)
14. Coad, A., Pellegrino, G., Savona, M.: Barriers to innovation and firm productivity. *Economics of Innovation and New Technology* 25(3), 321–334 (2015)
15. Castellani, D., Zanfei, A.: *Multinational Firms, Innovation and Productivity*. Edward Elgar Publishing (2006)
16. Jaureguy, M. V., Bianchi, C., Blanchard, P.: Financial and knowledge barriers to innovation. *Research Policy* 52(7), 104814 (2023)
17. Eurostat: *Community Innovation Survey 2018 (CIS2018)* (2022)
18. Szücs, F.: Research subsidies, industry–university cooperation and innovation. *Research Policy* 47(7), 1256–1266 (2018)
19. Symeonidis, G.: Innovation, firm size and market structure. OECD Econ. Dept. Working Papers No. 161 (1996)
20. Calvino, F. et al.: A taxonomy of digital intensive sectors. OECD Science, Technology and Industry Working Papers, No. 2018/14, OECD Publishing, Paris (2018)
21. Hölzl, W., Janger, J.: Innovation barriers across firms and countries, WIFO Working Papers No. 426 (2012)
22. Becker, B.: The Impact of Innovation Policy on Firm Innovation and Performance: A Review of Recent Research Developments. ifo DICE Report 17(04), 10–15 (2019)
23. Hair, J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., Anderson, R. E., Tatham, R. L.: *Multivariate Data Analysis*, 5th edn. Prentice Hall (1998)